

SCHOOL HEADS' COMMUNICATION AND MENTAL HEALTH SUPPORT TO WORK PERFORMANCE AND MOTIVATION OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

School heads must inspire their teachers to act to achieve common goals. Teachers who are motivated and productive in their endeavors ensure to play their role in uplifting society. Thus, this study focused on determining the impact of school heads' communication and mental health support on to work performance and motivation of teachers. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design with the researcher-made online survey questionnaire as the primary instrument in gathering the data needed. It was participated by the seven schools with 122 selected teachers in Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon on S.Y. 2020-2021. Analysis of the data revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between communication and mental health support of the school heads to the work performance of the teachers. Likewise, a significant positive relationship is found between communication and mental health support of the school heads to the motivation of the teachers. The study suggests that school heads can motivate and make the teachers perform better by communication and mental health support from them. School heads must figure out the factors which motivate the teachers most at work. By identifying and utilizing these factors, they can foster high performance and engagement at work. The results also revealed that family and community support significantly predict the work performance of the teachers. It also revealed that the non-verbal communication support and the social considerations and family and community support of the mental health support significantly predict the motivation of the teachers. Hence, strengthening relations between and among the school, family and community is a significant role that school heads may use in their management.

Keywords: Communication, Mental Health Support, Work Performance, Motivation